

Transport and Solute Separation Studies on Ion-exchange Membranes

KEHAR SINGH* and NEELAM MISHRA

Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur-273 009

Manuscript received 3 April 1995, revised 22 August 1995, accepted 27 October 1995

Membrane potential and membrane conductance studies have been carried out with a cation selective membrane (BNSCSM-1) to demonstrate predictability of solute separation characteristics of the membrane using non-equilibrium thermodynamic principles. Determination of membrane permselectivity and fixed charge density has been carried out. Variation of these electrochemical parameters with concentration has also been examined.

In the present investigation membrane potential and membrane conductance studies have been carried out using an ion exchange membrane (BNSCSM-1). Transport number, permselectivity and fixed charge density estimated using Teorell Meyer and Sievers (TMS) theory¹ were found to vary significantly with experimental conditions. Examination of the experimental results on the basis of non-equilibrium thermodynamics reveals that the given membrane is of considerable interest for the purpose of accomplishing electrodriven separations.

Results and Discussion

A membrane separating electrolyte solutions of unequal concentration exhibits a difference in electrical potential. This potential difference arises on account of unequal ionic mobilities and is equal to the so-called liquid junction potential when the membrane is non-selective. If on the other hand, the membrane is ideally selective the electrical potential which develops across the membrane is maximum and is given by¹

$$[(\Delta\phi)_{I=0}]_{\max} = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} \quad (1)$$

provided the solutions used are dilute. Here C_1 and C_2 denote concentrations of the electrolyte solutions. The experimentally measured membrane potentials using BNSCSM-1 membrane and NaCl, MgCl₂ and AlCl₃ solutions are included in Table 1. The liquid junction potentials calculated using the usual relationship²,

$$[(\Delta\phi)_{I=0}]_L = (2t_+ - 1) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} \quad (2)$$

and $[(\Delta\phi)_{I=0}]_{\max}$ values calculated using equation (1) are also given in Table 1 for the sake of comparison. These results clearly show that the membrane used in the present investigation is endowed with some selectivity. For a quantitative estimation of the extent of ion selectivity, a knowledge of transport number of ions in the membrane phase is essential, since permselectivity³,

$$P_s = (\bar{t}_+ - t_+)/(1-t_+) \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{t}_+$ denotes transport number of cation in the membrane phase. According to TMS theory, the membrane potential may be expressed as⁴

$$(\Delta\phi)_{I=0} = (2\bar{t}_+ - 1) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} \quad (4)$$

The validity of this relationship is examined in Fig. 1. The transport number values obtained from the slope of the curves were found to be $\bar{t}_{\text{Na}^+} = 0.931$, $\bar{t}_{\text{Mg}^{2+}} = 0.906$ and $\bar{t}_{\text{Al}^{3+}} = 0.898$.

Fig. 1. Examination of validity of equation (4) : (x) NaCl, (O) MgCl₂ and (●) AlCl₃.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE POTENTIAL VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS USING BNSCSM-1

Temp. = 35°, ΔC = 0.10 M, water content of membrane = 28.6%, Ion-exchange capacity = 0.0532 meq/g

Concn. of soln. (M)	Membrane potential (mV)			[(Δφ) _{I=0}] _{max} (mV)		
	NaCl	MgCl ₂	AlCl ₃	NaCl	MgCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0.06	48.5	28.5	16.2	62.5	31.2	20.8
0.10	26.2	11.7	7.2	28.6	14.3	9.5
0.15	16.2	6.9	3.7	18.1	9.0	6.0
0.20	11.2	4.5	1.5	13.3	6.7	4.4
0.25	8.8	3.0	0.5	10.6	5.3	3.5
0.30	6.7	2.3	0.7	8.8	4.4	2.9

TABLE 2—TRANSPORT NUMBERS, PERMSELECTIVITY AND FIXED CHARGE DENSITY VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Concn. of sol. (M)	NaCl			MgCl ₂			AlCl ₃		
	$\bar{t}_+$	P_s	$\phi\bar{X}$ mol dm ⁻³	$\bar{t}_+$	P_s	$\phi\bar{X}$ mol dm ⁻³	$\bar{t}_+$	P_s	$\phi\bar{X}$ mol dm ⁻³
0.06	0.962 0	0.936 1	0.319 4	0.956 1	0.923 4	0.288 7	0.963 0	0.941 5	0.335 3
0.10	0.957 6	0.928 9	0.501 7	0.940 9	0.897 7	0.407 5	0.877 3	0.806 1	0.272 4
0.15	0.948 5	0.913 9	0.675 4	0.882 0	0.797 0	0.395 9	0.807 3	0.695 4	0.290 3
0.20	0.920 7	0.867 7	0.698 1	0.838 1	0.722 5	0.417 9	0.669 0	0.476 8	0.216 9
0.25	0.916 4	0.860 7	0.845 3	0.783 9	0.630 9	0.406 6	0.429 0	0.097 5	0.048 9
0.30	0.882 1	0.803 7	0.810 5	0.762 3	0.595 1	0.444 3	0.380 2	0.020 4	0.012 2

Fig. 2. Variation of membrane potential with mean concentration : (x) NaCl, (O) MgCl₂ and (●) AlCl₃

Membrane potential data wherein the difference in concentrations is fixed at 0.10 M while varying the mean concentration, are presented in Fig. 2. Transport numbers obtained using relationship (4) are summarised in Table 2 along with permselectivity values obtained using equation (3) and the fixed charge density ($\phi\bar{X}$) is estimated using the relationship⁵,

$$\phi\bar{X} = \frac{2\bar{C}_s P_s}{\sqrt{1-P_s^2}} \quad (5)$$

These results clearly show that a significant alteration in electrochemical characteristics of the membrane occurs with variation in concentration. This could arise on account of alteration in the dimensional characteristics of the membrane when kept equilibrated with solutions of different concentrations. Accordingly, membrane constant of the system under investigation was determined using membrane conductance and the procedure described elsewhere⁶. The membrane constant (A/l) was calculated using the relationship,

$$\frac{A}{l} = K_m \frac{1}{k} \quad (6)$$

where, $A = \pi r^2$ is the effective cross-sectional area of the membrane, l the membrane thickness, k the specific conductance of the electrolyte and k_m the membrane conductance. The K_m values were derived in the usual manner from current voltage curves⁷. The calculated values of the membrane constant are included in Table 3 along with the membrane conductance values. When sodium chloride was used, a significant increase in membrane constant value with increase in concentration was observed. This change was not so conspicuous in other cases.

Fig. 3. Dependence of membrane conductance on concentration : (x) NaCl (O) MgCl₂ and (●) AlCl₃

TABLE 3—MEMBRANE CONSTANT AND MEMBRANE CONDUCTANCE VALUES AT DIFFERENT MEAN CONCENTRATIONS

Concn of soln. (M)	A/l			$10^3 \times K_m (\Omega^{-1})$		
	NaCl	MgCl ₂	AlCl ₃	NaCl	MgCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0.06	1.51	2.84	0.69	8.6	27.0	7.9
0.10	1.13	2.52	1.04	11.0	33.0	17.0
0.15	2.08	2.19	1.00	28.3	39.0	20.0
0.20	2.69	2.09	0.85	46.5	46.0	22.0
0.25	4.17	2.03	0.80	83.3	53.0	24.0
0.30	4.25	2.24	1.00	97.8	65.0	33.0

Ion exchange membranes in principle can be used for accomplishing electrolytic separation⁸. Methodology of non-equilibrium thermodynamics shows that separation characteristics of membrane can be derived with advantage on the basis of membrane potential and membrane conductance studies⁹. Solute fluxes estimated using the phenomenological approach outlined elsewhere¹⁰ along with deple-

tion in concentration when solutions of different concentrations are used, are included in Table 4 for different electrolytic systems. These results show possibility of the occurrence of significant electrodriven separations.

TABLE 4—PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS AND DEPLETION DUE TO ELECTRODRIVEN SOLUTE MIGRATION AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF NaCl, MgCl₂ AND AlCl₃ SOLUTIONS

Time = 1 h, Volume of solution undergoing depletion = 30 ml

Concn of soln (M)	NaCl		MgCl ₂		AlCl ₃	
	$\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta C}$	% depl	$\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta C}$	% depl	$\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta C}$	% depl
0.06	0.485	19.4	0.285	35.8	1.162	6.0
0.10	0.262	13.4	0.117	17.9	0.072	5.7
0.15	0.162	21.4	0.069	12.5	0.037	3.4
0.20	0.112	24.2	0.045	9.6	0.015	1.5
0.25	0.088	34.2	0.030	7.4	0.005	0.6
0.30	0.067	30.5	0.023	7.0	0.007	1.1

*In V mol⁻¹ dm⁻³

Experimental

Cation exchange membrane (BNSCSM-1) was received from C S M R I, Bhavnagar. Sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and aluminium chloride (Qualiger's), were used as such. Distilled water was used in the preparation of solutions. The experimental set-up described elsewhere¹⁰ was used for membrane potential and membrane conductance measurements. The membrane under investigation was fixed in an all-glass cell and kept overnight in contact with desired solutions. The solutions were renewed and membrane potentials recorded with the help of a HIL 2665 multimeter using saturated calomel electrodes (SCE). The solutions were repeatedly renewed till reproducible values were obtained. The membrane potential data were obtained using different unequal concentrations keeping the mean concentration fixed at $C = 0.05 M$ to obviate alteration in the dimensional and electrochemical characteristics of the membrane. With a view to investigating variations of membrane selectivity with concentration, measurements

were carried out wherein difference in concentration was fixed at $\Delta C = 0.10 M$ while varying the mean concentration. For membrane conductance measurements the current-voltage behaviour was examined. Known magnitude of potentials across the membrane were applied using SCE electrodes. For current measurements, silver-silver chloride electrodes along with a HIL 2142 multimeter were used. Conductance values were derived from the slopes of the current vs potential plots. All measurements were carried out at $35 \pm 0.25^\circ$.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Head Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University, for facilities and Dr. A. K. Tiwari for helpful discussions. The authors are also grateful to the Membrane Division, C.S.M.R.I., Bhavnagar for gifting the cation exchange Membrane.

References

- 1 N. LAKSHMINARAYANAIH, "Transport Phenomena in Membranes", Academic, New York, 1969.
- 2 T. R. BOLAM, "The Donnan Equilibrium", G. Bell and Sons London, 1932.
- 3 F. HEJFERRICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962; J. G. A. BILTER, "Transport Mechanisms in Membranes Separation Processes", Plenum, New York, 1991.
- 4 N. LAKSHMINARAYANAIH, "Membrane Electrodes", Academic, New York, 1976; "Electrochemistry in Biology and Medicine", ed. T. SHEDLOVSKY, Wiley, New York, 1955.
- 5 N. LAKSHMINARAYANAIH, "Equations of Membrane Biophysics", Academic, New York, 1987; K. SINGH, R. SHABD and V. N. SRIVAS TAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 391.
- 6 K. SINGH and A. K. TIWARI, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1987, 116, 42; S. R. DEGROOT, "Thermodynamics of Irreversible Process", North Holland, Amsterdam, 1963.
- 7 V. SUBRAHMANYAN and N. LAKSHMINARAYANAIH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 4314; A. K. CHAKRAVARTY, B. CHRISTENSEN and P. LANGER, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1985, 22, 111.
- 8 K. S. SPIEGLER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 54, 1409.
- 9 A. KATCHALSKY and P. F. CURRAN, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Harvard University Press, Cambridge, 1965.
- 10 K. SINGH and A. SINGH, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1993, 82, 141.